

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

The impact of the COVID-19 epidemic upon people's life aspects: An overview study

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2022, 14(02), 505–509

Publication history: Received on 29 March 2022; revised on 14 May 2022; accepted on 16 May 2022

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2022.14.2.0389>

Abstract

Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS-CoV-2), the causative agent of Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19), has recently promoted a rapid change in the way we place ourselves as working humans, so the Earth is already at a dizzying pace. It is developing. The Organization (WHO) classified COVID-19 as an epidemic in March 2020. Putting the entire world on high notice, and it quickly spread to uncharted territory. According to the findings, older persons are much more likely to contract COVID-19, and substantial illnesses, like diabetes, hypertension, and obesity are so much more likely to be impacted putting them at a higher risk of catastrophic disease and death. Even while children tend to have a are less likely to acquire the serious condition and require reduced hospitalization and oxygen therapy, they may suffer a multisystem aggressive disease.

Keywords: COVID-19; Impact; Life Aspects

1. Introduction

Coronavirus (COVID-19), a highly contagious respiratory infection, first surfaced and spread internationally in Wuhan, Hubei Province, Beginning December 2019 in China. The Health Organization said on March 11, 2020 this newly identified viral infection a worldwide health emergency (WHO) [1].

According to the WHO, the COVID-19 has spread globally, and governments in 213 countries are implementing a variety of steps to limit the COVID-19. To prevent and regulate viral transmission, governments launched a variety of measures on January 23, 2020, involving city-wide lockouts, security alert limitations, and physician supervision at residence [2]. As a response towards the COVID-19 epidemic threats, (CP) to medical systems and society at large, several more countries have introduced a massive global household guideline, the large percentage of which entail social exclusion and containment, in order to minimize the occurrence of new communicable disease and level the COVID-19 infectious disease curve. Gradient Social phobia and confinement can still have serious consequences, resulting in emotional distress as well as other unwanted mental health and psychological effects [3].

Fewer instances of COVID-19 have been recorded in Adults in the United States and around the world have lower IQs than children. Children make up about 22% of the population in the United States, but as of December 6, 2021, children make up more than 15% of all 19 COVID cases reported to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). In most cases, children's problems are minimal, and therapy consists solely of supportive care. According to the American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP), children account .Since the outbreak began on November 25, 2021, approximately 7 million children have been positive in the United States, accounting for 17% of all cases reported by age in 49 states. That's 9167 cases per 100,000 children. [4].

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Older people are at a much more risk of chronic disease after contracting COVID-19. This is a significant finding for the European Region, as we know that over 95% of these fatalities occurred in those over the age of 60. More than half of the fatalities were among those aged 80 and up. According to data, people with at least one underlying co-morbidity, notably those with cardiovascular disease/hypertension and diabetes, account for 8 out of 10 fatalities. [5]. China was the first to indicate that COVID19 mortality is highly related with age and climbs quickly with age, with males experiencing greater rates than females [6].

Public health measures such as quarantine, restricted movement, self-isolation, social distance, and "cocooning" have been used around the world to contain infections and protect people's safety [7]. Given the high risk of serious illness in people with comorbidity and those over the age of 60, these strategies have been more restricting to these populations [8]. This has resulted in many nations adopting a conservative public health policy, with a focus on encouraging older persons to stay at home [9]. In many countries school health services are often neglected this is reflected into lack of awareness and education about common illnesses and first-aid care [29].

2. The impact of the COVID-19 epidemic on children and adolescent social life aspect

Rapid withdrawal from school, social life, and out-of-work activities has had equal impact on children and adolescents. Domestic violence has become an increasingly problematic part of them. Stress has a direct impact on mental health as it leads to increased anxiety, changes in diet and school dynamics, anxiety, and even failure. [10].

Although school cancellations and a lack of outside activities have severely interrupted the routines of children and teenagers, they may or may not be completely separated. Most of the time, I have parents. Some children may not feel lonely in this situation because they spend more time with their families and less time on social media and the internet [11].

A recent study in China looked at 1036 isolated children and adolescents aged 6 to 15 years and discovered that 112, 196, and 68 of them experienced depression, anxiety, or both [12]. As a result of the COVID-19 outbreak, another study found that imprisoned children and adolescents in India were at increased risk of mental distress. These children were helpless (66.11%), worried and anxious (68.59%), and dread (61.98 percent) as compared to non-quarantined kids [13]. Furthermore, children and adolescents aged 3–18 years old in China showed indicators of inattention, clutching, worry, and irritability throughout the outbreak [14].

3. The impact of the COVID-19 epidemic on young and adult's bio-psycho-social and economic life aspect

The young are less susceptible to COVID-19, however, the consequences of a pandemic can be fatal. Children and adolescents may be particularly vulnerable to pandemic biopsychosocial stressors, understanding and understanding the disruptions in daily life as a result of social isolation, as well as the short- and long-term effects of outbreaks. Has an inexperienced ability to do. As soon as population-wide containment measures are implemented to contain the virus epidemic, they are adversely affected [15].

This global epidemic threatens to compound an Millions of young people are unable to secure jobs, start businesses and participate in society due to existing learning problems. The quality and availability of educational and development opportunities are very limited, especially for the most disadvantaged, and insufficient for young people who expect and deserve access to learning. The government aims to ensure learning continuity for approximately one billion students affected by the sudden closure of schools around the world by instantly adapting education and learning using digital and non-digital technologies. We are taking measures [16].

By the end of 2020, the OECD weighted average unemployment rate for 15 to 29-year-olds had reached 11.5 percent, equating to 19.1 million unemployed young people. At the start of the epidemic, unemployment was significantly higher among young women than among young males. Furthermore, many young people face physical-distance measures, remote learning, a decline in income, problematic household situations, and/or mental health concerns. The crisis is not hitting all young people equally, with those who were already experiencing greater hardships bearing a disproportionate share of the weight [17].

4. The impact of the COVID-19 epidemic on older people's biopsychosocial and economic well-being

COVID-19 pandemic has impacted populations all throughout the United States and worldwide. While the ramifications of the concurrent economic slump for older persons are just now being realized, previous experience shows that the effects might be disastrous for many. According to studies, more than one out of every five Americans aged 65 and over lives in areas with high infection rates and high economic instability concerns [18].

The COVID-19 epidemic had a good sized effect on maximum people's each day lifestyles with inside the first 1/2 of 2020. People had been removed due to substantial lockdown and preventive measures that have harmed the worldwide financial system and restricted get right of entry to bodily and intellectual fitness care. While those measures can be required to save you the virus from spreading, the adverse bodily, psychological, and societal outcomes are clear. As a result, generation has advanced to try and offset those outcomes, imparting customers with virtual options to many not unusual place activities. Of the daily tasks that can no longer be completed on a regular basis. However, the elderly population has received the fewest benefits from these digital tools, despite being disproportionately affected by both the infection and the lockdown measures [19].

The COVID-19 crisis, on the other hand, has brought with it a number of new difficulties, some of which are unrelated to the virus but are related to the global lockdown measures that have been enacted. While the lockdown may be necessary to control the infection, the virus's ramifications have already been documented, and they vary from physical to psychological. According to preliminary study, heightened stress, anxiety, and despair are among the psychological consequences of this crisis and the prolonged shutdown [20].

According to previous research, people over the age of 65 accounts for 80 % of COVID-19-related deaths. Full defensive precautions for the old have been reinforced and will need to be enhanced in some countries since the virus has largely targeted the old [21]. This suggests that the older will be disproportionately impacted by any unfavorable consequences that arise in the coming months [22].

Additionally, several communities nowadays are suffering the actual risk of increased mental health problems, with potentially severe long-term effects, as depression and stress induce faster cognitive decline and a higher prevalence of Parkinson disease among the elderly. Physical constraints on people's movement from outside their homes will almost probably increase this situation, resulting in less opportunity for activity for many individuals. Several studies have shown that low to moderate exercise dosages and intensities can significantly improve mental skills in the older, especially in those with cognitive deficiencies or psychiatric diseases [23].

As shown in a survey conducted, over 40% of older citizens are unable to be using telemedicine services because they lack the skills to do so effectively [24]. People aged 20–44 had the greatest acceptance of telemedicine usage during the epidemic, regardless of the fact that the older population had the highest annual frequency of medical provider visits [25, 26].

While seclusion is necessary to protect older persons from virus infection, it has resulted in Elderly people are becoming more lonely, isolated, and negatively stereotyped [27]. It is also associated with an increased risk of heart disease, anxiety, depression, cognitive decline, Alzheimer's disease, and mortality. On the other hand, meaningful social interactions have a health-protecting effect [28].

5. Conclusion

The COVID -19 Pandemic, which was discovered in late 2019, has created various obstacles and obstructions in all areas of life. The pandemic COVID -19 had a huge impact on people's lives; higher education institutions, industrial and commercial hubs all over the world were shut down, and people of all ages were affected by the pandemic's devastating effects, which the World Health Assembly (WHO) classified as a worldwide epidemic (emergency condition). Individuals (children, teenage boys, teenager, elders, and the elderly) from all over the globe have been affected by Covid-19's negative effects, whether it's educational and social consequences from the adaptation of home detention, an absence of community blending, the suspended of learning programmes in universities and schools, or financial stress from the complete withdrawal of several actions. The lack of financial caused by industrial manufacturing firms, and also the Corona disaster, had devastating effects on the health infrastructures in the most of the world's nations.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgment

My sincere gratefulness and thanks to. College of nursing- university of Basrah.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

There are no conflicts of interest and all researchers are compatible.

Statement of ethical approval

The present research work does not contain any studies performed on animals/humans subjects by any of the authors'.

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